

Automated Image Processing for Mycorrhizal Fungi Structure Analysis and Feature Extraction

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Abstract — Different organisms have been shown to create scalable, fault-tolerant, and efficient networks. Mycorrhizal fungi have an important ecological function and display interesting, yet poorly understood, network creation capabilities. Image analysis algorithms may provide a powerful tool for extracting meaningful quantitative information about fungal structures. Here, we discuss some recently developed solutions to automate the analysis of growing, filamentous biostructures and extract network information that might be functional to infer novel communication strategies and algorithms for robotic multi-agent systems or networking. At the same time, we provide effective analysis tools for improving the biological understanding of these natural systems and provide new knowledge for efficient forestry and agriculture management.

Keywords — *mycorrhizal fungi, network analysis, image analysis, bioinspiration.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Filamentous, growing organisms can generate complex network structures [1], [2]. For example, slime mold, without any central nervous system, can generate scalable, fault-tolerant, and efficient transport networks comparable to real-world complex systems such as the Tokyo railway infrastructure [3]. Mycorrhizal fungi are a type of fungus with a filamentous morphology called hyphae that form symbiotic relationships with plants, where the plant receives nutrients in exchange for sugar [4]. When the same fungal genets connects to multiple plants, a so-called Common Mycorrhizal Network (CMN) is formed, which allows plants to share information [5] and resources [6]. These biological networks have attracted attention due to their importance and potential to enhance ecological resilience [7] or improve sustainability in agriculture [8]. The hyphae grow from the apex and evolve through branching, when a new hypha divides from the main hypha, and anastomosis, when an apex merges into another hypha [1].

A mycorrhizal fungus generally evolves in a 3-dimensional network, which can easily reach a high degree of complexity. In previous works targeting the meaningful and quantitative interpretation of the network structure, the authors tried to reduce the complexity in 2D by cultivating a fungal organism on a thin plane. They acquired images through an optical microscope and applied various image analysis algorithms to automatically extract network

parameters [1], [2], [9]. Here, we propose a similar approach to analyze the structure of a mycorrhizal fungus called *Rhizophagus Irregularis*, which can establish symbiosis with crop plants (e.g., rice) and generate irregular paths originating from their spores [10]. We developed ad-hoc algorithmic solutions to process images from microscopy acquisitions and extract information about fungal structures: spores and hyphae. The extraction of fungal features, like the slime mold model, promises to provide novel solutions to coverage and exploration problems, multi-agent systems communication, and novel networking approaches. At the same time, deeper analyses of such natural systems would benefit forests and agricultural field management. An overview of our approach is sketched in Fig. 1a.

II. AUTOMATED ANALYSIS OF MYCORRHIZAL FUNGI

A. Culture of Model Organism and Image Acquisition

Spores of *Rhizophagus Irregularis* were cultured in 12×12 cm² Petri dishes following the protocol described in [11]. Since the resulting sample was 3-dimensional, the depth dimension could be captured by imaging the sample in multiple focal planes, generating a so-called Z-stack. We used a Nikon AZ100M microscope equipped with an Andor Zyla sCMOS camera (VSC-10642), AZ Plan Fluor 5× objective, and a white backlight for the acquisitions. The microscope sensor (camera) can move along 3 degrees of freedom. The NIS-Elements software (Nikon Instruments Inc.) was used to control the image acquisition [11].

B. Identification and Quantification of Fungal Spores

As a first step, we proposed an algorithm for automatically identifying and quantifying spores in a Z-stacked 3D sample and a technique to estimate the depth position of each spore [11]. The program is implemented in MATLAB [12] and computes at first the scale of the image, i.e., the length to which each pixel corresponds. The images in the Z-stack are then loaded one by one. Each image is resized to speed up computation. The MATLAB function *imfindcircles* is applied to identify the spores, and their center is extracted. However, the same spore is typically present in multiple focal planes with a slight spatial distortion (Fig. 1b). Close centers are thus clustered with *dbscan-clustering* [13] to group all the centers belonging to the same spore (Fig. 1c).

Fig. 1. a) Conceptual flow of the bioinspired approach. The biological model is the communication system established by plants through underground fungal networks. We characterize the fungal structures by in lab microscopy observations and analysis. Characteristic information concerning network dynamics can be translated in future for artificial robotic networks, e.g., to solve coverage problems during exploration tasks. We develop ad-hoc solutions to reconstruct network information. b) Example of spore detection with marked multiple centers for each spore. c) Closed centers are clustered to represent a single spore, circled in red in the image. d) Skeletonization result for filament detection. Borders of spores are also skeletonized. The spore algorithm detection provides a mask to overlap with the skeletonization and provides connection points between filament and spore. e) Example of single connection points detected for each spore. f) Example of an occlusion occurrence resulting in a spore with 3 connection points detected. g) Result of the algorithm correcting the occlusion. h) Example of a possible fungal network defined through our algorithm. Nodes are filament and edges their branches. Colors represent filament ridge prominence, and the degree defines the node size.

Determining the focal plane in which a given spore is more focused can estimate a given spore's relative depth position. The selection of the optimal plane for each spore was automated by maximizing a focus measure (FM). We proposed a specialized focus measure that calculates the gradient of a patch image encircling the spore and selects the Z-plane corresponding to the image having the maximal value around the circular border of the spore [11].

The program was validated by comparing the automatically obtained spore count with the spore count obtained through manual assessment. It was also shown that the Z-stack analysis significantly improved performance with respect to a plain 2-dimensional image.

C. Fungal Network Analysis

In earlier works, different strategies have been proposed for automatically generating an undirected morphological graph representing the network structure of a filamentous organism in a sample image. This process can split into two main steps: 1) segmentation or detection of the filament, and 2) vectorization, i.e., turning a binary image into a graph, where the junction points are represented as nodes and the filaments connecting the junctions as edges [14]. A recognized strategy for overcoming the first challenge is the application of algorithms detecting ridge features in the image [1], [2], [9], [15], [16]. A result of this step is shown in Fig. 1d. A limitation of the vectorization is that it does not consider the possibility that hyphae may cross each other [1], [2]. Unlike in many other species, the *Rhizophagus Irregularis* hyphae cross each other quite commonly, yielding an overestimation of the connectivity. We propose a geometric-based solution that partially overcomes this

limitation in two dimensions and tested our approach on different samples from [17]. We evaluated fungal filament segmentation performance by comparing the automated length count with a manual count and obtained a good agreement (Lin's Concordance Coefficient equal to 0.96, with a 95% lower confidence interval of 0.91). To evaluate the recognition of crossing, we had to distinguish between crossing and branching. From an image with 160 branches and 20 crossings, we were able to classify 155 true positive (TP), 1 false positive (FP), and 1 false negative (FN) branches, and 17 TP, 1 FP, and 1 FN crosses. These results demonstrate the high precision ($TP/(TP+FN)$ equal to 0.99 for branches and 0.94 for crossings) reached by our method. In addition, spores are opaquer than the hyphae, and occlusion occurs if a hypha grows in front of or behind a spore. To address this issue, we merged the spore and hyphae detection algorithms and defined a solution to correct artifacts and false connectivity introduced by the spores. Specifically, we detect the intersection points among spores and the filament (examples in Fig. 1e and f). We define the director vectors for the branches originated from the identified intersection points and through geometric parameters we identify the filament exiting from the spore (if any) and reconstruct the occluded segment between two points likely belonging to the same hypha (Fig. 1g). Testing the algorithm on 16 spores having 3-connection points, the reconstruction worked perfectly.

The fungal structure can now be transformed into an undirected morphological graph (Fig. 1h) for successive topological analysis that can eventually span over time.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Some microorganisms create growing network structures to explore their environment despite not having a brain. Mycorrhizal fungi are among these organisms and are exploited by plants to reach resources, e.g. phosphorus, that are not easily accessible to roots [6]. The growth dynamics and morphological features of these networks are still poorly understood. Since these networks have been shown to enhance the growth and resilience of plants connected to the CMN [4], eviscerating their features becomes essential to improving forestry and agriculture policies. At the same time, such biological systems can represent important models for robotics and networking, being natural representatives of complex systems.

Automation of sample assessment through image analysis seems a promising approach for extracting meaningful quantitative parameters of mycorrhizal fungi structures. We provided an overview of the image processing we developed to analyze spores and hyphae and proved enhanced performances by employing Z-stack information for network representation.

Controlled experiments conducted under diverse and mutable conditions may provide the data necessary to yield meaningful guidelines to develop robust communication strategies for robotic networks with scalability, fault tolerance, and efficiency.

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